

Online Companion: Embedding Dependencies Within Distributionally Robust Optimization of Modern Power Systems

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This manuscript serves as an electronic companion to [1]. Section 1 defines the Wasserstein probability metric. Sections 2 and 3 provide the final optimization model under the metric-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_1$ and the copula-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_2$, respectively. The real-time operational problem for the out-of-sample simulation is given in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 gives the economic and technical input data of our case study built upon the IEEE reliability test system.

1 Wasserstein ambiguity set

The distance between two distributions, namely $\mathbb{Q}_1$ and $\mathbb{Q}_2$, is assessed via the Wasserstein metric, whose mathematical formulation is given in Definition 1.1. This metric can be seen as an optimal transportation problem that aims to minimize the cost of transporting the probability mass from $\mathbb{Q}_1$ to $\mathbb{Q}_2$.

Definition 1.1 (*Wasserstein metric [2]*) *The Wasserstein metric $d : \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is defined as*

$$d(\mathbb{Q}_1, \mathbb{Q}_2) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\Pi \in \Xi^2} \int \|\tilde{\xi}_1 - \tilde{\xi}_2\| \Pi(d\tilde{\xi}_1, d\tilde{\xi}_2) \\ \text{s.t. } \Pi \text{ is a joint distribution of } \tilde{\xi}_1 \text{ and } \tilde{\xi}_2 \\ \text{with marginals } \mathbb{Q}_1 \text{ and } \mathbb{Q}_2, \text{ respectively} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (1)$$

The objective function in (1) represents the transportation cost of moving the probability mass from $\mathbb{Q}_1$ to $\mathbb{Q}_2$. The chosen cost for moving each data sample is the norm $\|\tilde{\xi}_1 - \tilde{\xi}_2\|$, defined as the Wasserstein distance. The joint distribution Π , which is the optimization variable, refers to the optimal transportation plan. Based on this definition, the Wasserstein metric-based ambiguity set collects the closest distributions from an empirical one $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{\tilde{\xi}_i}$, that is typically constituted of N observed samples, each assigned with probability $\frac{1}{N}$. We thereby mathematically define the Wasserstein ambiguity set as follows:

$$\mathcal{M}_1 = \left\{ \mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{F} \mid d(\mathbb{Q}, \hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N) \leq \theta_1 \right\}. \quad (2)$$

2 Model reformulation under metric-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_1$

$$\min_{\substack{g, \bar{r}, \underline{r}, V, \lambda, \sigma_i, \gamma_i, \\ \tau_i, \lambda_i, \sigma_{g,i}, \gamma_{g,i,1}, \gamma_{g,i,2}, \\ \bar{\tau}_g, \bar{\lambda}_g, \bar{\sigma}_g, \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1}, \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}, \underline{\tau}_g, \underline{\lambda}_g, \underline{\sigma}_g, \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1}, \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}}} c^\top g + \bar{c}^\top \bar{r} + \underline{c}^\top \underline{r} + \lambda \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } g + \bar{r} \leq p^{\max} \quad (3b)$$

$$g - \underline{r} \geq 0 \quad (3c)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{r} \leq r^{\max}; 0 \leq \bar{r} \leq r^{\max} \quad (3d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top g + \mathbf{1}^\top W \mu - \mathbf{1}^\top d = 0 \quad (3e)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V + \mathbf{1}^\top W = 0 \quad (3f)$$

$$\begin{cases} c^\top V \hat{\xi}_i + \gamma_i^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \sigma_i & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \gamma_i - c^\top V\|_* \leq \lambda & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \gamma_i \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \quad (3g)$$

$$\left. \begin{cases} \bar{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\bar{\lambda}_g \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ V_g \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{r}_g - \bar{\tau}_g + \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1} - V_g\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1} \geq 0; \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2} \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \right\} \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3h)$$

$$\left. \begin{cases} \underline{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\underline{\lambda}_g \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ -V_g \hat{\xi}_i - \underline{r}_g - \underline{\tau}_g + \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1} + V_g\|_* \leq \underline{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}\|_* \leq \underline{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1} \geq 0; \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2} \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \right\} \forall g \in \mathcal{G}. \quad (3i)$$

3 Model reformulation under copula-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_2$

$$c^\top g + \bar{c}^\top \bar{r} + \underline{c}^\top \underline{r} + \alpha \theta_1 + \beta \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i \quad (4a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{g, \bar{r}, \underline{r}, V, \alpha, \beta, \sigma_i,} \\ & \zeta_{wi}^{(1)}, \zeta_{wi}^{(2)}, \mu_{wi}^{(0)}, \mu_{wij}^{(1)}, \mu_{wij}^{(2)}, \mu_{wij}^{(3)}, \mu_{wij}^{(4)}, \mu_{wij}^{(5)}, \mu_{wij}^{(6)}, \\ & \bar{\alpha}_g, \bar{\beta}_g, \bar{\tau}_g, \bar{\nu}_{gi}, \bar{\zeta}_{gwi}^{(1)}, \bar{\zeta}_{gwi}^{(2)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(0)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(1)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(2)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(3)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(4)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(5)}, \bar{\mu}_{gwi}^{(6)}, \\ & \underline{\alpha}_g, \underline{\beta}_g, \underline{\tau}_g, \underline{\nu}_{gi}, \underline{\zeta}_{gwi}^{(1)}, \underline{\zeta}_{gwi}^{(2)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(0)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(1)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(2)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(3)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(4)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(5)}, \underline{\mu}_{gwi}^{(6)}, \end{aligned} \quad (4b)$$

$$\text{s.t. } g + \bar{r} \leq p^{\max} \quad (4b)$$

$$g - \underline{r} \geq 0 \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{r} \leq r^{\max}, 0 \leq \bar{r} \leq r^{\max} \quad (4d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top g + \mathbf{1}^\top W \mu - \mathbf{1}^\top d = 0 \quad (4e)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V + \mathbf{1}^\top W = 0 \quad (4f)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & -\zeta_i^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \zeta_i^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \mu^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{j=1}^N (\mu_{ij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\max} - \mu_{ij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\min} + \mu_{ij}^{(6)\top} \mathbf{1}) \leq \sigma_i & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & V^\top c + \zeta_i^{(1)} - Q^\top \mu_i^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\mu_{ij}^{(4)} + \mu_{ij}^{(3)}) = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \frac{1}{N} \zeta_{wi}^{(2)} - \mu_{wij}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_{wi} - \mu_{wij}^{(2)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} - \mu_{wij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} + \mu_{wij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} + \mu_{wij}^{(5)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} - \mu_{wij}^{(6)} \leq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \mu_{wij}^{(1)} + \mu_{wij}^{(2)} + \mu_{wij}^{(3)} - \mu_{wij}^{(4)} - \mu_{wij}^{(5)} = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\zeta_i^{(1)}\|_* \leq \alpha & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\zeta_i^{(2)}\|_* \leq \beta & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{aligned} \right. \quad (4g)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \bar{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\bar{\alpha}_g \theta_1 + \bar{\beta}_g \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\sigma}_{gi} \right) \leq 0 \\ & -\bar{\tau}_g - \bar{\tau}_g - \bar{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \bar{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{j=1}^N (\bar{\mu}_{1gij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{1gij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{1gij}^{(6)\top} \mathbf{1}) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{gi} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & -\bar{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \bar{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{j=1}^N (\bar{\mu}_{2gij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{2gij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{2gij}^{(6)\top} \mathbf{1}) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{gi} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & V_{gw} + \bar{\zeta}_{1gwi}^{(1)} - Q^\top \bar{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\bar{\mu}_{1gwi}^{(4)} + \bar{\mu}_{1gwi}^{(3)}) = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \bar{\zeta}_{2gwi}^{(1)} - Q^\top \bar{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\bar{\mu}_{2gwi}^{(4)} + \bar{\mu}_{2gwi}^{(3)}) = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \frac{1}{N} \bar{\zeta}_{vgwi}^{(2)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_{wi} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(2)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} + \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(5)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(6)} \leq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(1)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(2)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(3)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(4)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(5)} = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\bar{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(1)}\|_* \leq \bar{\alpha}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\bar{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(2)}\|_* \leq \bar{\beta}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{aligned} \right. \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4h)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \underline{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\underline{\alpha}_g \theta_1 + \underline{\beta}_g \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \underline{\sigma}_{gi} \right) \leq 0 \\ & -\underline{\tau}_g - \underline{\tau}_g - \underline{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \underline{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \underline{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{j=1}^N (\underline{\mu}_{1gij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\max} - \underline{\mu}_{1gij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\min} + \underline{\mu}_{1gij}^{(6)\top} \mathbf{1}) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{gi} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & -\underline{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \underline{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \underline{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{j=1}^N (\underline{\mu}_{2gij}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\max} - \underline{\mu}_{2gij}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}^{\min} + \underline{\mu}_{2gij}^{(6)\top} \mathbf{1}) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{gi} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & -V_{gw} + \underline{\zeta}_{1gwi}^{(1)} - Q^\top \underline{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\underline{\mu}_{1gwi}^{(4)} + \underline{\mu}_{1gwi}^{(3)}) = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \underline{\zeta}_{2gwi}^{(1)} - Q^\top \underline{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\underline{\mu}_{2gwi}^{(4)} + \underline{\mu}_{2gwi}^{(3)}) = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \frac{1}{N} \underline{\zeta}_{vgwi}^{(2)} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_{wi} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(2)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(3)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} + \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(4)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\min} + \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(5)\top} \bar{\xi}_w^{\max} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(6)} \leq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(1)} + \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(2)} + \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(3)} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(4)} - \underline{\mu}_{vgwi}^{(5)} = 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\underline{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(1)}\|_* \leq \underline{\alpha}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & \|\underline{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(2)}\|_* \leq \underline{\beta}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{aligned} \right. \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G}. \quad (4i)$$

$$(4j)$$

4 The real-time operational problem

This section presents the real-time operational optimization problem for the out-of-sample analysis. Given the realized uncertainty $\widehat{\xi}_j$ that refers to the wind power forecast error with respect to the day-ahead forecast μ , this problem writes as

$$\min_{V, \Delta d, \Delta w} c^\top V \widehat{\xi}_j + v_{\text{Shed}}^\top \Delta d \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } 0 \leq \Delta d \leq d \quad (5b)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta w \leq W(\mu + \widehat{\xi}_j) \quad (5c)$$

$$-\underline{r} \leq V \widehat{\xi}_j \leq \bar{r} \quad (5d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V \widehat{\xi}_j + \mathbf{1}^\top W \widehat{\xi}_j + \mathbf{1}^\top \Delta d - \mathbf{1}^\top \Delta w = 0. \quad (5e)$$

The objective function (5a) models the total recourse operational cost, incurred by the recourse production cost of conventional generating units (the first term) and the load shedding cost (the second term). The parameter $v_{\text{Shed}} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{D}|}$ refers to the value of lost load. The wind spillage cost is assumed to be zero. Constraints (5b) and (5c) limit the wind power spillage $\Delta w \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{W}|}$ and the load shedding $\Delta d \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{D}|}$. The recourse production $V \widehat{\xi}_j$ of conventional generating units is limited in (5d) by the reserve capacities $\underline{r}$ and $\bar{r}$ procured in the day-ahead stage. The real-time power balance is ensured by (5e).

5 Input data

We build our case study upon the IEEE reliability test system [3]. All economic data are available in [4]. The input data are given by Table 1. It includes technical data of conventional generating units, including their production cost c_p in \$/MWh, upward reserve capacity procurement cost $\bar{c}_p$ in \$/MW, downward reserve capacity procurement cost $\underline{c}_p$ in \$/MW, capacity g_p^{max} in MW, maximum upward regulation capability $\bar{r}_p^{\text{max}}$ in MW, and maximum downward regulation capability $\underline{r}_p^{\text{max}}$ in MW. In addition, Table 1 includes the day-ahead wind power forecast μ in MW and their installed capacity $W_{(w,w)}$ in MW. Finally, this table gives the input data of 17 loads, including their consumption d in MW and the value of lost load v_{Shed} in \$/MWh.

Table 1: Input data

Conventional generating units		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12					
c_p [\$/MWh]		13.32	13.32	20.7	20.93	26.11	10.52	10.52	6.02	5.47	7	10.52	10.89					
$\bar{c}_p$ [\$/MW]		1.68	1.68	3.30	4.07	1.89	5.48	5.48	4.98	5.53	8.00	3.45	5.11					
$\underline{c}_p$ [\$/MW]		2.32	2.32	4.67	3.93	3.11	3.52	3.52	5.02	4.97	6.00	2.52	2.89					
g_p^{max} [MW]		106.4	106.4	245	413.7	42	108.5	108.5	280	280	210	217	245					
$\bar{r}_p$ [MW]		48	48	84	216	42	36	36	60	60	48	72	48					
$\underline{r}_p$ [MW]		48	48	84	216	42	36	36	60	60	48	72	48					
Wind farms												1	2					
Installed capacity [MW]												500	500					
Day-ahead wind power forecast [MW]												120.54	115.52					
Loads		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12					
d [MW]		84	75	139	58	55	106	97	132	135	150	205	150	245	77	258	141	100
v_{Shed} [\$/MWh]		500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

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